

**SOCIO-ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF KUSAVALI VILLAGE IN MAVAL TAHSIL OF PUNE
DISTRICT IN MAHARASHTRA, INDIA**

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Abstract:

Kusavali village as part of the rural settlement which can always effect the rural environment of nearby location. Socio-economic status of Kusavali village is mostly depended on education, income and occupation. Socio-economic condition makes much effect on housing condition, living condition, life style, education, health and other all functions in rural area. The education and income are important elements for Socio-economic assessments of rural population.

The study was carrying out on the basis of primary data including the field survey with help of questioners and also collect the secondary data from grampanchayat of kusavali village. This paper represent the Socio-economic assessments of Kusavali village with help of following parameters like, labour Force Participation, Agricultural Labour, Educational status, Language, Culture, Religion & Caste status.

Key Wards: - Field Survey, Spatial Analysis, Maps, graphs, Tables and Various statistical techniques.

1. Introduction:

Kusavali village is small village in Maval tahshil. The village Kusavali is developed with cultural as well as social factors. Geographer's role is to understand this stage of cultural development and its relationship with natural environment.

The survey provides the primary data regarding different aspects of life style of man in the village. Environment has direct impact on village culture. Natural phenomenon directly governs the village setup. Therefore it is very important to study natural phenomenon along with human beings. The government of India and government of Maharashtra continuously try to develop the villages, as the 3/4th of the Indian population lives in this habitat. Government introduces many schemes for people's welfare. Urban people have least contact with villagers therefore it is necessary to visit the village to see the percolation extent of government plans and schemes to find out the problem and finally to conclude the suggestion.

2. Objective:

- To study the economic status of Kusavali village.
- To understand the social aspects of study area.

3. Methodology:

The primary data and secondary data have been used for the research paper. The questionnaire has been prepared to collect the data. The statistical method has been used for data calculation.

3.1: Data collection:

Data collection has done with the help of the observation, interviews, photos, Google images and field survey. Questionnaires have prepared for obtaining information of solid waste & tin-bin system. However spatial analysis of study area has been done on Google image using Arc GIS in to calculate area and related features.

Topographical map is very important tool for geographers. Give the Toposheet no 47 F/8 with the help of this Toposheet we got the following information.

- Location of study area.
- Relief of study area & surrounding area.
- Drainage around the study area.
- Different natural and cultural aspects of village eg. Settlements, Road, Forest etc.

4. The location of Study area:

The Village Kusavali is located between $18^{\circ} 52'41''$ N latitudes and $73^{\circ}30'80''$ E longitudes at 658m mean sea level in the taluka of Maval, district of Pune, in the State of Maharashtra. It is located 54 KM towards west from District head quarters Pune and 85 KM from State capital Mumbai. Kusavali Pin code is 412106 and postal head office is Vadgaon (Pune). Village Vahangaon is situated in north of Kusavali, in the eastern side Nagathali village is situated, village Vadeshwar is situated in south-western side and in the south of Kusavali Shradhe village is situated. Marathi is the Local Language here.

Fig. No. 1: Location Map of Study area

Source: GPS Survey by Researcher

5. Economic Structure:

Economic structure gives an idea about the economic status of the village. It studies the economic condition of agriculture activity on which the development of the village depends. It includes economic factors like availability of labour, capital, and use of fertilizers, irrigation and technology.

5.1. Man Power:

The below table shows the distribution of main workers during the year 2015. We can conclude from the studied data that in the year 2015 the percentage of male workforce 54.37% and female workforce is 45.63 % in that case we see that female workforce is less and male workforce is more.

Table No.6: Man Power

Gender	Population	Percentage (360)
Male	137	195.71
Female	115	164.29
Total	252	360

Fig. No.7: Man Power

5.2. Marginal Workers:

We find in village Kusavali most of the people do not have enough land which they can still on their own to earn and living so they are mostly dependent on the other works that available to them. According to survey there are 36 (83.72%) Male and 7 (16.28%) female are found as a marginal workers.

Table No.7: Marginal Worker

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	36	83.72%
Female	7	16.28%
Total	43	100

Fig. No.8: Marginal Worker

5.3. Non – Workers:

In the non-workers category we find mostly children and elderly people who are Incapable of doing works, we can see in the village out of total population 27.03 comprising of non- workers in which 60 (60%) male and 40 (40%) are female population.

Table No.8: Non – Workers

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	60	60
Female	40	40
Total	100	100

Fig. No.9: Non – Workers

5.4. Gender wise Farmers:

In rural main occupation of people is farming. They either work in their own land or for somebody else. There are 177 farmers in2015 out of which 88(49.72. %) are male & 89 (50.28%) are female farmers.

Table No. 9: Gender wise Farmers

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	88	49.72
Female	89	50.28
Total	177	100

Fig. No.10: Gender wise Farmers

5.5. Agricultural Labour:

From the above table it can be shown that in Agricultural Labour males are more which contribute 58.62% than females which contribute 41.38%.

Table No.10: Agriculture Labour

Gender	Population	Percentage (%)
Male	34	58.62
Female	24	41.38
Total	58	100

Fig. No.11: Agriculture Labour**6. Social Structure:**

The objective of the social study of the village is to examine the population standard of living, facilities available in the village. And other factors like Trade, Transport, settlement, Hospital and School etc.

Following parameters will consider for under-standing social structure.

6.1. Standard of living:

The standard of living in Kusavali is medium to low. Most of the people in the village are workers. Some people are working in their own firm. A large number of people working in small piece of land, which they have inherited or they work in other field. Some of them migrate to cities for work or education purpose. The service man families have slightly upgraded and medium standard of living

6.2. Educational Status:

Education is necessary for the development of every sphere of human activity. It is the most important tools for income of household, health, hygiene and standard of living. The Village has an Anganwadi, a primary school name as Zillah Perished Primary School serves the Purpose of primary education.

Table No. 11: Educational Status

Class	Male	Female
00	65	67
1-4	36	21
5-10	88	71
11-12	13	8
13-15	1	0
Other	1	0
Total	204	167

Fig. No.12: Educational Status

Above table shows the 5 to 10 std. population is more & above 13-15 STD population is less. It indicates that the area of Kusavali is less educated.

6.3. Language:

Generally all the people use talk in Marathi in all surveyed families. Their mother tongue is Marathi. They use this language while talking within them. Marathi language is the mother tongue in all surveyed families.

6.4. Culture:

As a village of Maharashtra this village Kusavali also shows custom and culture Peculiar to the village. The village gaothan has a Goddess temple. There were various groups such as Bhajanimandal, TarunMandal, Dhol-Tasha Mandal etc. The festivals like Mhasoba yatra, Ganapati, Navaratra are celebrated in the village.

6.5. Caste status:

As per details from the study area the ST category constitute the majority community in study area & it has 46 (63.88%). After the ST category second majority community has other SC category. It has 23.61% schedule Caste action OBC has 4.17% respectively.

Table No. 12: Caste status

Caste	Family No.	Percentage(360)
Open	06	30
ST	46	230
SC	17	85
OBC	03	15
Total	72	360

Fig. No.13: Caste status

7. Conclusion:

The aims & objectives stated for this study which has been supportively elaborated and interpreted by the many findings and conclusion driven the various ways of this study. The conclusions were elaborated in the following ways.

They are mostly dependent on the other works that are available to them. According to survey there are 36 (83.72%) Male and 7 (16.28%) female are found as marginal workers. It can be shown that in Agricultural Labour males are more which contribute 58.62% than females which contribute 41.38%. Educational level is very low in Kusavli village. Above table shows the 5 to 10 std. population is more & above 13-15 STD population is less. It indicates that the area of Kusavali is less educated. As a village of Maharashtra this village Kusavali also shows custom and culture peculiar to the village. The village gaathan has a Goddess temple. There were various groups such as Bhajanimandal, TarunMandal, Dhol-Tasha Mandal etc. The festivals like Mhasoba yatra, Ganapati, Navaratra are celebrated in the village.

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